

THE ROLE OF OXIDATIVE STRESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION AND HYPERTENSIVE RETINOPATHY

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Abstract: Hypertensive retinopathy is a retinal vascular disease caused by high blood pressure. Symptoms usually appear in the later stages of the disease. Ophthalmoscopy reveals fundus arteriolar spasms, pathological arteriovenous shunts, changes in the vessel wall, flame-like hemorrhages in the fundus, cotton wool spots, yellow solid exudates, and optic disc swelling. Treatment includes monitoring blood pressure and local therapy to prevent vision loss.

Keywords: Pathophysiology, Clinical manifestations, Diagnostics, Treatment

Introduction:

A sharp increase in blood pressure leads to reversible spasm of the retinal vessels; Hypertensive crisis can lead to swelling of the optic disc. Longer and more pronounced episodes of increased blood pressure provoke an exudative reaction from the retinal vessels, thereby leading to damage to the endothelium and the development of necrosis. Other changes (for example, thickening of the walls of the arterioles, pathological arteriovenous shunting) develop after many years of high blood pressure. Smoking exacerbates the manifestations of hypertensive retinopathy.

Arterial hypertension is also a significant risk factor for other types of retinal lesions (for example, retinal artery or retinal vein occlusion, diabetic retinopathy). The combination of arterial hypertension and diabetes mellitus significantly increases the likelihood of vision loss. Also, patients with hypertensive retinopathy have an increased risk of damage to the vessels of other internal organs.

Arteriosclerosis with moderate ("copper wire" symptom) to severe ("silver wire" symptom) changes and signs of thickening of the vessel wall

In some cases, occlusion of the lumen of the retinal vessels may develop. The appearance of arteriovenous shunts is a harbinger of occlusion of the branches of the central retinal vein.

This photograph shows narrowing of the retinal arterioles as a result of thickening and opacity of the vascular walls (copper wire sign) caused by hypertensive atherosclerosis.

Hard exudates are intraretinal collections of fluid originating from capillaries. These exudates, especially in severe hypertension, may give the macula a star-like appearance. In severe hypertension, swelling of the optic nerve head develops (papilloedema indicates hypertensive crisis).

Diagnosis of hypertensive retinopathy

The diagnosis is made based on the history (duration and severity of arterial hypertension) and ophthalmoscopy data.

Hypertensive retinopathy is primarily treated by normalizing high blood pressure. Other factors affecting vision should also be monitored. In cases of vision loss, treatment of retinal edema with laser therapy or intravitreal injection of corticosteroids or anti-VEGF drugs (e.g. ranibizumab, bevacizumab, pegaptanib - the latter are not registered in the Russian Federation) may be effective.

Chronic hypertension causes progressive damage to the retina, which causes no symptoms until significant changes occur.

Chronic hypertensive retinopathy is recognized by the following signs: persistent narrowing of the arteries, abnormal arteriovenous cross-section (Salus sign), atherosclerosis with moderate changes in the vessel wall (copper wire sign) or more pronounced hyperplasia and thickening of the vessel wall (silver wire sign).

Hypertensive crisis can cause retinopathy with superficial flame-like hemorrhages; small, white, superficial foci of retinal ischemia (cotton-wool spots); yellow solid exudates, and optic disc swelling.

Treatment is primarily through blood pressure control, and in some cases, retinal detachment, laser therapy, or intravitreal corticosteroids or anti-VEGF drugs are used.

Research methods and materials: Retinal detachment is the separation of the neurosensory cell layer of the retina from the underlying pigment epithelium. The most common cause is a tear (rupture or, less commonly, a hole) of the retina (rhegmatogenous detachment). Clinically, retinal detachment manifests itself as a decrease in central or peripheral vision, which is often described as the appearance of a dark veil blocking the field of vision. Other symptoms include painless visual changes, such as flashes of light or a sharp increase in floaters before the eyes. Retraction of the narrow veil and serous detachments (without retinal rupture) lead to loss of central or peripheral vision. Diagnosis is made using ophthalmoscopy. If it is ineffective, the presence and type of detachment can be determined using ultrasound. If rhegmatogenous retinal detachment develops acutely and significantly impairs central vision, urgent treatment is required. Treatment of rhegmatogenous retinal detachment may include closure of retinal tears using laser or cryotherapy, support of the retina using scleral buckling, pneumatic retinopexy, and/or vitrectomy.

There are 3 types of retinal detachment: rhegmatogenous (associated with its rupture), tractional, and serous (exudative). Tractional and serous retinal detachments are not associated with rupture and are called non-rhegmatogenous.

Gravitational detachment may occur due to tension in the area of vitreoretinal adhesions that form in proliferative diabetic or sickle cell retinopathy.

Serous detachment occurs when fluid leaks into the subretinal space. Causes include severe uveitis, especially Vogt-Kayanagi-Harada disease, choroidal hemangioma, and primary or metastatic choroidal cancer (see Cancers affecting the retina).

Retinal detachment occurs painlessly. The first signs of rhegmatogenous detachment include multiple dark or glassy, irregularly shaped, floating spots in front of the eyes (especially if they suddenly increase in size), flashes of light (photopsia), and blurred vision. As the detachment progresses, patients often notice the appearance of a veil or gray film in the field of vision. When the macula is involved, there is a significant deterioration in central vision. Simultaneous hemorrhage into the vitreous cavity may develop. In the early stages, traction and serous (exudative) detachment may be asymptomatic, sometimes causing blurred vision.

Indirect ophthalmoscopy visually demonstrates retinal detachment and allows to determine the type of detachment in almost all cases. With direct ophthalmoscopy using a portable ophthalmoscope, retinal detachments, for example, peripheral, can sometimes be missed. Therefore, to examine the peripheral areas of the fundus, indirect ophthalmoscopy with scleral pressure, with excessive abduction of the eye, examination with a slit lamp or a three-lens lens is necessary.

If examination of the retina is difficult due to vitreous hemorrhage (which may be accompanied by detachment), cataract, corneal clouding, or traumatic injury, then a B-mode ultrasound of the eye should be performed.

Although retinal detachment due to retinal tear is usually localized, it can spread to the entire fundus if not treated promptly (1). Any patient with a confirmed or suspected retinal detachment should be evaluated by an ophthalmologist.

If patients experience a sudden increase or decrease in floaters, photopsia, a veil or haze in the field of vision, sudden, unexplained loss of vision; or, if a vitreous hemorrhage is occluding the retina, an ophthalmologist should urgently perform indirect ophthalmoscopy to rule out retinal detachment.

Rhegmatogenous detachment is treated using one or more of the following methods, depending on the location and cause of the detachment. These methods include closing the retinal tear using laser therapy or cryotherapy. Scleral buckling involves placing a piece of silicone on the sclera, which binds the sclera and pushes the retina inward, reducing its tension on the vitreous. During this procedure, fluid is also removed from the subretinal space. Other treatments include pneumatic retinopexy (injection of air into the vitreous body) and vitrectomy. Non-detachable retinal breaks can be closed with laser photocoagulation and transconjunctival cryopexy. Almost all types of retinal detachment can be treated surgically (reattachment of the retina).

Non-rhegmatogenous retinal detachment due to vitreoretinal traction can be treated with vitrectomy; exudative retinal detachment due to uveitis can be treated with systemic corticosteroids or immunosuppressants (eg, methotrexate, azathioprine, drugs that inhibit tumor necrosis factor [TNF] activity). Alternatively, transudative detachment due to uveitis can be treated with periocular corticosteroid injections, intravitreal corticosteroid injections, or intravitreal dexamethasone implantation. Primary and metastatic choroidal cancer also requires treatment. Choroidal hemangiomas are treated with local photocoagulation or photodynamic therapy.

Risk factors for rhegmatogenous retinal detachment include myopia, previous cataract surgery, ocular trauma, and retinal degeneration.

All forms of retinal detachment cause blurred vision; early signs of rhegmatogenous detachment may include irregularly shaped vitreous floaters (especially if they suddenly enlarge) and flashes of light (photopsia).

If a patient suddenly experiences increased or changing floaters, photopsia, blurred or hazy vision, sudden unexplained vision loss, or vitreous hemorrhage occluding the retina, urgent indirect ophthalmoscopy should be performed by an ophthalmologist to diagnose retinal detachment.

Treatment of rhegmatogenous retinal detachment includes closure of retinal tears (using laser or cryotherapy), closure of retinal tear sites using scleral buckling, pneumatic retinopexy, and/or vitrectomy.

Non-rhegmatogenous detachment caused by vitreoretinal traction can be treated with vitrectomy, while transudative detachment due to uveitis can be treated with topical or systemic corticosteroids or systemic immunosuppressants.

Results: Retinal pigmentary dystrophy is a slowly progressive bilateral degeneration of the retina and its pigment epithelium caused by various genetic mutations. Clinical manifestations include night blindness and loss of peripheral vision. Diagnosis is made by ophthalmoscopy, which shows bone-spiked pigmentation at the equator of the retina, narrowing of its arterioles, and waxy pallor of the optic disc, posterior subcapsular cataracts, and vitreous pits. Diagnosis is confirmed by electroretinography. Retinyl palmitate (vitamin A), omega-3 fatty acids, and lutein with zeaxanthin can slow the process of vision loss.

The cause of retinal pigment dystrophy is a genetic disorder in the coding of retinal protein synthesis (several genes have been identified). The inheritance of genes can be autosomal recessive, autosomal dominant, and rarely X-linked. Retinal pigment dystrophy can be part of a symptom complex (for example, Bassen-Karnzweig syndrome, and Lawrence-Moon syndrome). One of these syndromes also includes congenital deafness (Usher syndrome).

Discussion: The pathological process affects the rods of the retina, leading to a gradual deterioration and in some cases a complete loss of night vision, sometimes starting in early childhood. Over time, night vision may be lost. In advanced cases, the circular scotoma gradually grows (detected by visual field testing) and central vision may also deteriorate. As the macula becomes increasingly damaged, vision decreases and this process can progress to virtual blindness.

Retinal pigmentary dystrophy should be suspected in all patients with decreased night vision and a positive family history. The diagnosis is made on the basis of ophthalmoscopy supplemented with electroretinography. Other types of retinopathies that resemble retinitis pigmentosa should be excluded - those associated with syphilis, rubella, phenothiazine or chloroquine toxicity, and extraocular cancer.

To determine the nature of the inheritance, all family members of the patient should be tested (with their consent). This group of patients should also receive genetic counseling before conceiving a child.

Summary: The changes caused by retinitis pigmentosa are irreversible, but in selected patients, the progression of the disease can be slowed by oral administration of vitamin A palmitate at a dose of 15,000 IU per day. Patients taking vitamin A palmitate should have their liver function monitored regularly. Supplementation with lutein and zeaxanthin may also slow the rate of vision loss (1).

In patients with cystoid macular edema, oral carbonic anhydrase inhibitors (eg, acetazolamide) or topical carbonic anhydrase inhibitors (eg, dorzolamide) may provide some improvement in vision (2). Voretigen neparovvec-rzyl is currently available for the treatment of retinal dystrophy associated with a confirmed biallelic RPE65 mutation. This is an adenoviral targeted gene therapy that is surgically injected into the subretinal space in patients with retinal cells and this specific mutation (3). This treatment can restore ambulatory vision in these patients. For patients with complete or near-complete vision loss, epiretinal and subretinal computer chip implants can restore some visual sensation.

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